

LEXICAL FOUNDATION OF TEXT TRANSLATION

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to linguistic unit at the level of a word in the source language, for example, in a certain profession, when any relevant name specific to the culture of the source language appears, a double-field adjective; words denoting objects, phenomena, and elements that are inherent in the original or functionally appropriate for the traditional naming of the culture of the culture, but that do not exist in the culture of translation or have a different management and order.

Key words: *profession, linguistic unit, sentence, phenomena, elements, language, activity, transferring, definitions, stylistic, source text, level.*

Due to the fact that English uses the Latin alphabet, and Russian uses the Cyrillic alphabet, when translating from English, there are difficulties associated with the transfer of proper names and names. The fact is that the same English proper name is translated into Russian in different ways. For example, William and William (William), Huxley and Huxley (Huxley), Watson and Watson (Watson). The same name Charles, if it refers to the English kings of the Stuart dynasty, is transmitted as Charles (for example, Charles I, who was executed during the English bourgeois revolution of the 17th century), and at the present time (even if this is the heir English throne) - like Charles. Why is this happening? Does this mean that there are no clear rules for the transfer of proper names?

The thing is that English proper names used to be translated using transliteration, i.e., the transfer of a graphic, alphabetic form of a word (literally from Latin: trans litera - through a letter) without taking into account phonetic transcription. By transliteration,

proper names are transmitted historically or traditionally: Dr. Watson (and not Watson) in Conan Doyle, since the book about Sherlock Holmes is more than a hundred years old; Greenwich meridian (it passes through the city, whose name is pronounced Greenwich), etc. There are other cases of two variants of the transfer of the name (surname). We can give an example with the surname Huxley. They are Huxley, the 19th century natural physicist, and Huxley, the 20th century English writer. All other attempts to use only transliteration when transmitting proper names instead of transcription, where possible, constitute a violation of the established norm. However, over time, when transferring proper names, transcription began to prevail, i.e., the phonetic (sound) way of depicting a name (surname) in Russian letters. For example, the surname Campbell is Campbell, the name Robert is Robert, etc.

Literal translation consists in the word-for-word reproduction of the text in units of the target language, if possible, preserving even the order of the elements in essence, literal translation is relatively rarely used for communicative purposes and usually has an exclusively scientific scope[4]. Thus, for the purposes of linguistic analysis, literal translation is considered to be preferable to other ways of presenting the source text, since it allows conveying information about the very syntactic structure of the original.

Semantic translation consists in the possibility of a more complete transfer of the contextual meaning of the elements of the source text in terms of the target language. The process of semantic translation is a natural interaction of two strategies: the strategy of focusing on the mode of expression adopted in the target language, and the strategy of focusing on preserving the features of the original form of expression[1]. The first strategy is applied to commonly used lexical and grammatical elements of the source text, such as standard syntactic structures, sentence length, typical metaphors, morphological structures, widespread general cultural and popular scientific terms and expressions, etc. The second strategy is appropriate. when translating non-standard, author's phrases, original stylistic devices, unusual vocabulary, etc.

Semantic translation, as a rule, is applied to texts that have a high socio-cultural status: important historical documents, works of high literature, unique epic samples,

etc. It is also required when transferring texts such as technical instructions, most scientific publications and, of course, legal documents[3].

The communicative method consists in choosing such a way of transmitting the initial information, which leads to a translated text with an adequate initial impact on the recipient. The main object in this method of translation is not only the linguistic composition of the source text, but also its substantive and emotional-aesthetic meaning. Moreover, unlike functional translation, communicative translation does not allow either reductions or simplifications of the source material. In essence, what in everyday life is often called literary and, in particular, literary translation, in fact, is precisely a communicative translation that takes into account - or programming - the pragmatics of the recipient. This method is optimal for most fiction, journalism, part of scientific-theoretical and popular science texts, etc.

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